

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and
Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

Containerized version of EC-Earth4 running
on one EuroHPC platform
Milestone M1.3

ESiWACE3 Milestone M1.3

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Porting container in D1.5 from NSC-Freja to EuroHPC platforms

A working containerised version of EC-Earth4 was delivered in D1.5. The reader is referred to the D1.5 report¹ for technical details on the containerisation. In this approach, all EC-Earth code was containerised including the python scripts to prepare model experiments and the scheduler for the HPC (SLURM). The container was shown to work on NSC-Freja but had to be built with versions of MPI and SLURM to match those on the host.

	Freja	LUMI	MareNostrum5
CPU	AMD Epyc 9354	AMD Epyc 7763	Intel Xeon Platinum 8480
Scheduler	SLURM 22.05.8	SLURM 23.02.7	SLURM 23.02.7
Container	Apptainer	SingularityCE	Singularity*
PMI	PMIx 4.2.6	Cray-PMI 6.1.14	PMIx 4.2.6
OS	Rocky Linux 9.5	SUSE Linux Enterprise Server 15 SP5	RHEL 9.2

Table 1: Hardware and software on Freja and the two EuroHPC platforms tested. *No outside connections allowed on MN5 so it is not possible to build container.

It was not possible to run the container built on Freja (in D1.5) on LUMI or MareNostrum5. On LUMI, the scheduler was missing several plugins necessary for submitting jobs. After adding these plugins to the container, it was discovered that the scheduler must be built with support for the HPE Slingshot interconnect to work on LUMI. It was not possible to add this to the container as the interconnect software is proprietary software from HPE. On MareNostrum5, the user is not allowed to read the “slurm.conf” file to gather information about the scheduler settings which is necessary for the container to work.

Modifying container for use on NSC-Freja and two EuroHPC platforms

The container was rebuilt by lifting SLURM out of the container and instead relying on the host SLURM implementation. This presents a big change from the container in D1.5. The user must now retrieve the EC-Earth code from git.smhi.se and build the necessary conda environment to prepare experiments, and then submit an experiment. EC-Earth4 will then submit a job to the queue using the “sbatch” command from the host to start the model on the host. All necessary input and forcing files will be copied to a work directory on the host and the “rdy2cpl” software will run to prepare remapping files for the OASIS coupler. The host then launches the model in the container, e.g. for the ocean component NEMO:

```
export APPTAINER_BINDPATH=/path/to/work/dir/,/opt/ece-4/run
srun -n 64 apptainer exec --pwd /opt/ece-4/run /path/to/container/ecec.sif nemo.exe
```

which binds the work directory on host to a run directory in the container.

¹<https://zenodo.org/records/13827671>

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The new implementation of the container can be built on Freja and run successfully on MareNostrum5. The container can also run on LUMI, provided that the container is built with MPICH rather than OpenMPI as only MPICH is ABI compatible with the Cray-MPICH on LUMI.

The container stack(s) are now:

1. base OS (AlmaLinux) + development tools
2. PMI_x
3. OpenMPI or MPICH
4. HDF5
5. netCDF
6. conda environment
7. EC-Earth4

but (2) is not used when building for LUMI. Note that the conda environment is necessary as the build scripts for EC-Earth4 used for (7) are written in python.

Technical issues on LUMI

We note that the EuroHPC platform LUMI has general issues with building and running containers which extend beyond this milestone. Several key components of the software, e.g. MPI library, interconnect, and process-manager interface (PMI), are proprietary software from HPE/Cray and are thus not available to us when building containers on Freja for porting to LUMI. The container, ECEC built on Freja, can still be run on LUMI as long as it is built with the MPICH library which is ABI compatible with the Cray-MPICH library.

We also note that ECEC is significantly slower on LUMI than on Freja and MareNostrum5. This is a known issue with containers on LUMI and may be mitigated by building the container with MPICH and binding the host Cray-MPICH library. However, as we can not build the container on LUMI, the bind must be done at runtime.

Other EuroHPC platforms such as MareNostrum5 as well as Freja do not suffer from the above issues as they use open-source softwares such as OpenMPI and OpenPMI_x.

Future improvements to the container

- 1) Upgrading EC-Earth4 to the latest version (OpenIFS from 43r3 to 48r1 etc)
- 2) Containerise python scripts to prepare experiments so that the user does not have to build any conda environments
- 3) Integrate binding of host MPI into EC-Earth to improve throughput on LUMI